

EXPERIMENTAL SUB-COMPONENT INVESTIGATION OF WIND TURBINE BLADE RETROFIT REINFORCEMENT

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ABSTRACT

During periodic inspection of wind turbine blades in various wind farms longitudinal cracks have been detected on blade surfaces in the vicinity of the trailing edge bondline. The edgewise cyclic forces acting on the wind turbine blade generate an out-of-plane deformation of the shell between the trailing edge and the internal shear web, which may lead to a fatigue failure of either the adhesive joint between the two trailing panels or the connection between the shell and the girder box.

With the purpose of reducing the deformations causing the premature failure of the wind turbine blade, the company Bladena has developed the D-String[®] retrofit reinforcement. The D-String[®] product consists of two conical plugs inserted in the sandwich trailing panels connected by a tie-string, placed in different positions along the blade. For the sub-structure tests, samples of trailing edge (including the connection with the girder box) were cut from a 34 m wind turbine blade manufactured by SSP-Technology A/S. Static as well as fatigue test were carried out, comparing the results obtained with and without the installation of the D-String[®] between the trailing panels, in order to assess the effectiveness of this retrofit reinforcement.

1 INTRODUCTION

Longitudinal cracks have been discovered at the trailing edge (TE) of wind turbines as a consequence of in-service loads. These cracks cause reduction of the wind turbine's performance and they may eventually lead to blade failure. Superficial cracks are an indication of defects in the underlying material. Edgewise cyclic forces acting on the wind turbine blade generate an out-of-plane deformation of the trailing edge panels (this behaviour of the TE panels is also known as "Breathing"), with consequent peeling stress concentrations at the adhesive joint between the two trailing edge panels and at the connection between the shell and the girder box, as shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Longitudinal cracks generated from peeling stress concentration at TE bondline and at the glued joint between girder box and TE panels.

With the purpose of reducing the deformations causing the premature failure of the wind turbine blade, the company Bladena has developed the D-String[®] retrofit reinforcement. The idea behind the D-String[®] product is to develop a device which will partially constrain the two trailing panels,

reducing the out-of-plane deformation hence the peeling stress concentration responsible for cracks growing.

The D-String[®] product consists of two conical plugs inserted in the sandwich trailing panels connected by a tie-string, placed in different positions along the blade. Integrated with the string is the so-called Fuse, which functions as an overload protection device in case of unexpected overloading.

Many tests were already carried out on each single D-String[®] component. In this paper focus is given to the evaluation of the overload protection device properties and to the improvement the D-String[®] can provide in terms of fatigue operational life-time, once installed between the trailing panels of a wind turbine blade. All the tests presented in this paper, along with the ones carried out in the past, are sub-component tests useful for the retrofit device development and carried out prior to an in-field, full-scale or sub-structural test of a wind turbine blade integrating the D-String[®] reinforcement, where the effectiveness of the reinforcement can be assessed under realistic operational conditions.

2 D-STRING[®] RETROFIT REINFORCEMENT

The D-String[®] product consists of the following components:

- Cones – the cones are installed in the trailing edge sandwich panels and are the anchoring points of the reinforcement string;
- String – the reinforcement string connects the cones on each side of the trailing edge panel.
- Fuse – the fuse is an integrated part of the reinforcement string and has the function of overload protection device in case of unexpected overloading.

All operations needed for installing the D-String[®] reinforcement on the wind turbine must be carried out at hub height in order to avoid demounting the blade from the hub, which would result in high additional costs. The idea is then for a retrofit crew to repel down from the wind turbine hub, installing cones and strings between the suction and pressure side in different positions along blade's trailing edge. Special tools are designed with the exclusive purpose of installing the reinforcement device. When installed, the string must be pre-tensioned at a certain load value, so that the device can mitigate the “breathing” of the trailing edge panels.

Figure 2: D-String[®] concept and position on the blade (left), and D-String[®] components (right).

3 OVERLOAD PROTECTION DEVICE TESTING

The first experimental investigation in this study refers to the fuse activation load, i.e. the load that must be applied at the string's ends causing the relative slide of the two portions of string into the overload protection fuse. Static as well as fatigue test were carried out. The primary function of the fuse is to allow the string to release tension, once the load exceeds a certain design level. Hence the integrity of the trailing panels will not be jeopardized by the reinforcement device, since it will be inactive for exceptional loading conditions.

The TE panels of a wind turbine are exposed to loads and deformations acting cyclically over the operational life time of the blade. Hence the most important aspect to be tested is indeed the fatigue life of the reinforcement. Anyway, static tests were carried out first in order to evaluate the static fuse activation load. Consequently, the fuse was tested in fatigue using different load levels.

The tests were performed using two different machines, a 25 kN and 250 Nm MTS 858 axial-torsion servo-hydraulic machine with a 25kN load cell mounted, and a 10 kN MTS 858 axial servo-hydraulic machine mounted with a 10kN load cell. In order to clamp the string's ends to the hydraulic grips of the test machines, two discs with a cylindrical cross-section were used and the string secured at each end using a bowline, a simple knot used to form a fixed loop at the end of a rope.

A total of 12 static tests were carried out. The results are reported in Table 1.

Test number	Max Load [kN]	Test number	Max Load [kN]
<i>ST 1</i>	1,454	<i>ST 7</i>	1,200
<i>ST 2</i>	1,682	<i>ST 8</i>	1,933
<i>ST 3</i>	1,593	<i>ST 9</i>	1,706
<i>ST 4</i>	1,475	<i>ST 10</i>	1,548
<i>ST 5</i>	1,355	<i>ST 11</i>	1,794
<i>ST 6</i>	1,349	<i>ST 12</i>	1,334

Table 1: Summary of the static tests done on the overload protection device.

The average fuse activation load detected from the static tests is 1,535 kN, with a standard deviation of 0,206 kN.

The string-fuse interface was also tested for fatigue loading conditions. The tests were controlled in force, using a starting maximum force value of $F_{max}=1000N$ and a lower value of:

$$F_{min} = 200N + 0.1 F_{max} \quad (1)$$

where 200N is the value of pre-tension applied to the string, when installed between the trailing edge panels. The results obtained are reported in Table 2, pointing out F_{max} , F_{min} and the number of cycles needed for activating the fuse.

Test number	F_{max} [N]	F_{min} [N]	Cycles at fuse activation
<i>FT 1</i>	1000	300	2500
<i>FT 2</i>	1000	300	418'850
<i>FT 3</i>	1000	300	181'350
<i>FT 4</i>	950	295	Run-out (2 mln.)
<i>FT 5</i>	950	295	Run-out (2 mln.)
<i>FT 6</i>	950	295	3850
<i>FT 7</i>	950	295	127'400
<i>FT 8</i>	900	290	Run-out (2 mln.)
<i>FT 9</i>	900	290	Run-out (5 mln.)
<i>FT 10</i>	900	290	Run-out (5 mln.)
<i>FT 11</i>	800	280	Run-out (5 mln.)
<i>FT 12</i>	800	280	Run-out (5 mln.)
<i>FT 13</i>	800	280	Run-out (5 mln.)
<i>FT 14</i>	450	245	Run-out (10 mln.)
<i>FT 15</i>	450	245	Run-out (10 mln.)
<i>FT 16</i>	450	245	Run-out (10 mln.)

Table 2: Summary of the fatigue tests carried out on the overload protection device.

When the maximum load applied at each cycle is higher than 900N, the fuse-string connection exhibits an unreliable behavior, with some specimens failing after few cycles and others reaching the threshold (fixed at 2 million cycles for the first 8 tests). However, for load levels lower than 900N all

specimens were run-out, even using a higher threshold number of cycles (5 or 10 million cycles in some cases). Due to the unreliability of the results above 900N and the consistent number of run-outs at lower loads, it is hard to visualize the results in a S-N diagram. It is anyway possible to conclude that the fuse-string connection will not fail in fatigue under operational loading condition, estimated around 100-200N [5]. The last 3 tests were carried out at loads which are closer to operational circumstances (considering 200N of pre-tension). The tests were stopped after 10 million cycles without having experienced any sliding of the string into the overload protection device, demonstrating the reliability of the fuse design at in-service loading conditions.

4 BREATHING TEST

The breathing test is a method for simulating the Mode 1 peeling stresses arising at the trailing edge bondline during in-service loading conditions. The out-of-plane deformation of the panels causes peeling stresses at the trailing edge bondline as well as at the adhesive joints between the aft shear web and trailing panels. The aim of the test is to introduce out-of-plane deformation equivalent to what is observed in operating turbines. The test is performed on D-String[®] reinforced specimens and on specimens without reinforcements. The tested specimens are cut-outs from a 34 m wind turbine blade manufactured by SSP-Technology A/S. They consist of the trailing panels and the aft shear web. Static tests were performed using a 25 kN Instron 8872 universal servo-hydraulic testing machine with a 25 kN load cell mounted, while fatigue tests were carried out in a 10 kN MTS 858 servo-hydraulic testing machine equipped with a 10 kN load cell.

4.1 Test set-up

The breathing behavior of the trailing edge is simulated by using the test set-up shown in Fig. 3. Two load application clamps are attached to each of the trailing edge panels at the mid-point. The load is applied through spherical hinge joints which allow rotation of the specimen while the panels deform out-of-plane. This method of constraining the specimen ensures that only peeling forces from the out-of-plane deformation are introduced in the bondline, as well as ensures that no drilling or crushing of the trailing edge sandwich panels occur. The chosen position of the load clamps coincides with where the D-String[®] reinforcement is installed. For this reason holes are introduced in the load clamps to facilitate the D-String[®].

Figure 3: Breathing test set-up; concept (left) and real set-up on a specimen where the D-String[®] is installed (right).

4.2 Static tests

On operational wind turbine blades, the structure undergoes a loading condition which is cyclic over its life time. For this reason, the best way to evaluate the performances of the reinforcements developed for stiffening the structure is to perform fatigue testing of such devices once installed into the blade sub-structure. It is however needed to first execute static testing in order to quantify the failure load of the sub-structure, and thus decide which load levels should be used for fatigue testing.

Static tests have been performed using the breathing test set-up on two specimens: one with D-string[®] and one without. In Fig. 4 the force-displacement curves obtained from the static tests are reported. It is observed that the initial slope of the force-displacement curve for the D-String[®] reinforced specimen is higher than for the specimen without reinforcement, hence the D-String[®] provides additional stiffness to the trailing edge. It is also observed that the maximum load capacity for the unreinforced specimen is approximately 0,8kN, whereas the D-String[®] reinforced specimen has a maximum capacity of approximately 1,5kN, which is the activation load for the overload protection fuse. The force-displacement curve for the D-String[®] reinforced specimen shows secondary peaks, corresponding to each time the fuse has been activated (i.e. the relative slide of the two portions of string). Failure occurs when the displacement reaches about 45 mm, generating critical peeling stress concentrations at TE bondline and consequent opening of the TE panels at the bondline.

Figure 4: Force-Displacement curves for static breathing test.

4.3 Fatigue tests

The trailing edge specimens have been tested under fatigue loading conditions in order to evaluate the improvement of the sub-structure life time, when reinforced with the D-String[®]. Two fatigue tests were initially carried out, one without reinforcement and one equipped with D-String[®], using the same loading condition. Both tests were controlled in load, with a maximum load per cycle of 750N and a minimum of 200N at 1 Hz. These load values have been decided based on the static test results and equivalent to approximately 90% of the static failure load detected for the specimen without the D-String[®].

The first test was carried out on the specimen without reinforcement, which failed after only 4800 cycles. This early collapse was expected, since the maximum load at each cycle was close to the static failure load. Failure occurred since a crack started growing at the TE bondline, and then it continuously propagated causing the failure of the glued joint.

The crack has been monitored over time. In Fig. 5 it is possible to visualize the crack opening during the fatigue test. The pictures refer to an early stage of the test, when about 1000 cycles had elapsed.

Figure 5: Crack opening during the fatigue test on the not reinforced trailing edge specimen. The load is at its lower (left) and highest (right) level per cycle.

The second test was carried out on a D-String[®] reinforced specimen. The same loading conditions were used in order to achieve a first estimation of the improvement related to the installation of the D-String[®] between the trailing edge panels. In this second case, the maximum load per cycle corresponds to the 50% of the static first fuse activation load. The test was stopped after 1 million cycles and the fuse was never activated. No cracks were detected by visual inspection during the test. The D-String[®] acted as reinforcement for the sub-structure preserving the TE bondline from the peeling stress concentration responsible of crack growth.

As mentioned, the fuse did not activate during the fatigue breathing test. This was predictable looking at the fatigue test results from the overload protection device, since no specimens experienced fuse activation for loads lower than 900N.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Overall the experimental investigation of the D-String[®] retrofit reinforcement has produced good initial indications in terms of improvement of fatigue life time of the trailing edge sub-structure. With reference to the fatigue tests carried out, the reinforcement has decreased the peeling stress concentration at the TE bondline and at the connection between the trailing edge panels and aft shear web, which were addressed as the main responsible for longitudinal cracks growing at the trailing edge. Up until now only few fatigue tests have been carried out. More breathing fatigue tests will be carried out with the purpose of building a S-N curves for both the D-String[®] reinforced specimens and the not reinforced ones, in order to assess the structural fatigue lifetime improvement the D-String[®] concept can facilitate.

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